

Investigating Rhetorical Devices in Men and Women's English Diaries

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Abstract--- The purpose of this research is to investigate the stylistic aspects of diaries written by both men and women. The problem of the study lies in the difference between men and women in the way they express their thoughts and feelings. Therefore, the study attempts at showing the stylistic features which demonstrate the differences found in the diaries written by men and women as far as rhetorical devices are concerned. To achieve these aims, the study hypothesizes that rhetorical devices are more frequently used by women than by men. The data collected include ten diaries, five of which belong to men and the other five belong to women. To carry out the stylistic analyses as regards the data, the study has adopted Leech and Short's model with some modifications made on it to be more appropriate for the purpose of the study. It is found here that women use more rhetorical devices than men.

Keywords--- stylistic analysis, Diaries, Rhetorical devices, men, women.

Introduction

Life writing is a non-fiction literary writing on subjects of personal experience and observation. It includes biography, autobiography, memo, diary and letter. A diary is narrating of one day to day diary as a non-fiction genre in a private place where people can keep their thoughts, feelings, and opinions of everything from morning to the night of only one day. There are all different types of diaries, like food diaries, health diaries, or academic diaries. But a diary does not have to be specific if people do not want it to be, it can also just be a place where people write about whatever they want.

People may learn a lot about a person's personality qualities, likes and dislikes, as well as their way of life, by reading their diary. As a result, it should be stored carefully. People may learn a lot about themselves by keeping a diary. Keeping a diary assists students to clarify their thoughts and writing about their accomplishments as well as their ideas.

Some people use their diary to keep track of their daily activities, putting down the happenings of the day in a very accurate manner. One of the diarists kept track of the baseball league and games in her diary. Others are very reflective, viewing diary writing as a means of expressing oneself on paper and revealing some of their most private thoughts. The concept of being entirely honest is very important to them. They are writing for themselves in the future: why would you want to read anything again if it is false? Another diarist drew a picture of himself every night to 'write' his diary.

Digital processes change quickly, and when new software is produced, older software becomes obsolete. Digital approaches have put the diary genre in jeopardy more than ever before. The vulnerability of paper is well-known, while the vulnerability of digital data is less so. As the example of 'Open Diary' shows, phones and computers break down, software becomes unavailable, and data is lost. 'Open Diary', which began in 1998 and lasted sixteen years, was an internet platform where users could submit their daily notes. The site just vanished one weekend in 2014, along with all of its material. Thousands of individuals were left without their manuscripts. As a memorial to 'Open Diary', one penned an elegiac tribute toward what she called "the cemetery of vanished words."

Stylistics and Style

Stylistics examines the text in detail and evaluates the key language. It's quite close to practical critique when it comes to forms for sake of interpretation. In reality, Short (2013:1) defines stylistics as " an approach to the analysis of (literary) texts using linguistic description" .Stylistics is a branch of linguistics that bridges the gap between literature and linguistics. As a result, depending on how you look at it, stylistics might resemble either "linguistics" or "literary criticism."

Stylistics, according to Jeffries and McIntyre (2010:1), "is a sub-discipline of linguistics concerned with the systematic investigation of language style and how it varies depending on variables such as genre, context, historical time, and author."

Literary stylistics seeks to explain, either implicitly or explicitly, the links between language style and aesthetic function. From the standpoint of a linguist, the most important question is: why did the author choose this mode of expression over another?(Hussein and Abdul Ameer,2017:7).

Stylistics is the linguistic analysis of literary language. This is a rather deceptive term: the term "style" was historically given two distinct types of language, such as religious or legal writings. Both of these variants are now referred to as registers. In the meantime, the terms style and stylistics have taken on the relatively restricted, restrictive meaning of linguistics applied to literature. Literary language is frequently erroneous. Typically, some characteristics have been emphasized or foregrounded, frequently by making them unusual (Carter & Stockwell, 2008: 44).

Style can be linked to people, genres, times, or languages, according to Lehman (1996:303). Shakespeare's works are credited to him by scholars due to his style. The Renaissance period is linked with one style, whereas the Age of Enlightenment is connected with another. The French are supposed to have a distinct style, but German is generally thought to be cryptic. As a result, the usage of people, genres, times, languages, and style has a wide range of applications. Style, according to Leech and Short (2007:9), alludes to Ferdinand de Saussure's linguistic concepts of parole and langue. That is, the method a single user of a language performs the language's code reference rather than the language investigating the language's entire attributes. Experts go on to say when someone talks about "a style" or "X's style," they are referring to what's common or repeating in a text. Stylistics has always been engaged with literary language, they

claim. To put it another way, it frequently tries to explain the connection between literary and style or aesthetic function (Ibid:10). As a result, style is linked to parole: a style is created by selecting from a large language repertoire (Short and Leech, Ibid.) In truth, style authors have had a diverse variety of viewpoints on the subject, with one point of dispute being the question of "To what or whom do we ascribe style?"

Style, in its broadest definition, can refer to both speaking and writing, as well as 'everyday' and 'literary' sorts of language; nonetheless, it is traditionally associated with written literary literature, and it is in this sense that we will be concerned (Ibid.).

A writer's style is the way he or she uses language in a particular literary work. That is, it has to do with how a writer uses words (diction) and how those words are organized in sentences and longer units of speech.

Diaries:

Diaries are papers or recordings of events and experiences kept by someone at regular intervals; they usually include a few formatting features that give the text structure as someone read it. In general, like a letter, entries are typically dated, chronologically ordered, and possibly addressed to the specific recipient. Others start with the words "Dear Journal" or "Dear Diary," and are written to a real, deceased, or fictional person. In diaries, self-reports strive to capture events as they happen at the moment (Fothergill, 1974:95).

The diary's narrative is brief, distinct by combining novels and narration essays, that is, it ought to be a new and original literary demonstration, with the author's unique and personal views and ideas. The author is the primary character in the diaries. He or she travels through time, delivering us "rich, complex, and arcane stuff from those eras." (Galstyan, 2014:3-4).

Diaries are examples of "factual prose" or a language which lacks in-depth analysis and generalization and instead depends solely on the story to show the facts. Diary entries are a "systemic sort of speech: narration with aspects of logic, reasoning with components of description, as well as a free writing system" in its literary form (Skirgailo, 2006:150).

Because diaries are composed of a series of entries, an entry can be regarded as a core of the diaries, and its structure dictates the book's overall layout. In most diaries, each entry usually corresponds to a single day (Jackson, 2010:70-76).

Diary Categories:

Due to the difficulty of creating a complete description of the diary, it is typically split down into smaller descriptive sections. External factors can impact this, as well as the diarist's habits or self-imposed labels. Diarists, for example, have typically targeted certain audiences or functions with personalized diaries, influencing who wrote and how. Readers may observe the intentions of authors, the consequences of different diary formats and media, diarists' judgments about what to include or avoid, and the significant patterns that diarists establish and apply in their writings by thinking about diaries by category. Diaries fall to many categories, demonstrating the genre's versatility once again. The following are some examples of popular daily diaries (Henderson, 2019:8-9):

Diary apps, Personal diary, Letter diaries, pocket diaries, bullet journals, sex diaries, gratitude diaries, dream diaries, blogs, travel diaries, illness diaries, devotional diaries, confessional diaries, pregnancy diaries, witness diaries, prison diaries, school diaries, spiritual diaries, war diaries, multiyear diaries, work diaries, vlogs (Ibid.).

Personal diaries will be investigated out of all of these types of diaries in this research.

Diary as a Form of Spoken Language:

According to Miller (1984), most of the linguistic features that have been established in empirical research to distinguish women's speech, such as the increased use of exclamations, questions, and sentence fragments, are typical characteristics of spoken language in general. As a result, women's speech contains more signs of spoken language than men's speech, such as writing for journals and women's publications. These features contribute to the prose's logical flow, which Woolf refers to as "pliancy," which is open-ended, indeterminate, and multi-directional. The dialogic aspect of a genre that may be understood as a means of informing oneself about oneself, as Julien Green puts it, and the proximity of diary language to spoken language can be considered in terms of the relationship between the diary and the familiar letter (Jackson,2010:122-123).

Diary language, on the other hand, is much more than just recorded conversation. Despite the fact that Diary is punctuated in a normal manner, with the dash used sparingly and in a conventional manner, it is full of incomplete sentences (Ibid.). For example, Benjamin Haydon's diary, which was literally held open when he died and whose writing continuously alludes towards feelings that go beyond written language, is one of the diaries with the most dashes. These gestures toward openness are frequently associated with endings. The diary even has a dash at the conclusion, with a last entry that is notable for its ambiguity between openness and closure (Jackson,2010:123):

"God forgive—me—Amen.

Finis

of

B.R. Haydon

‘Stretch me no longer on this tough World’—Lear.

End—(223)"

Online Diaries:

Nowadays, the majority of people keep a diary, a simple activity that exists for a long time. It is a fantastic method to express diarists' life and keep track of what are they thinking, what their desire is, what they have done, and what they accomplished. A diary has been characterized as a personal, handwritten record of a particular person's experience, views, and remarks at the times of inscription for hundreds of years. Despite the reality that the diary is a diverse and heterogeneous cultural form, it frequently represents the record of an 'I' who constructs an

image of them in connection to the entire world. Diary writing, as a daily cultural tradition, requires both meditation and expression(Neef et al.,2006:116).

Digitalization has had an impact on practically every element of public and private life, and the diary is no exception. Millions of people (particularly teenagers and young adults) are now actively engaged in 'blogging,' making it a popular genre on the web. Up until the age of computers, the concept of the script was crucial to the materiality of diaries: the idea of a diary is usually associated with (hand)writing, signalling not only genuineness but also personality. The handwriting has traditionally been viewed to indicate information about the writer's personality, particularly age and even psychiatric features, with graphology becoming the study that discovers this information. The initial 'technologizing of the word,' the accessibility of paper and a pen, stimulated the need to make that person readable to the current self or to the 'other' (Ong,1982). As a result, writing is closely linked to a certain stage of one's development. According to Sonja Neef (2006:118), handwriting is an embodied practice: moving a pen onto paper necessitates a direct connection between the body and screenplay, an act in which the eye and hand are deeply interlinked with the technology of paper and pen, and the techniques for providing them (Neef et al.,2006:118).

A diarist's instruments have emerged as a new technology that really has gradually supplanted handwriting. As a result, writing with a pen and paper varies from writing with a text editor or a typewriter. Typewriter, on the other hand, generates a new connection between authors, words, and representations; handwriting not merely structures but often develops reflections and thoughts. It is probable that typewriters' lack of popularity with diary writing was owing to the sound of fingers slamming on a keyboard, which, unlike handwriting, distanced the physical intimacy of body and text. One approach to storing self-reflective papers evolves as writing technology advances. Handwritten diaries have a physical presence (Neef,2006:118-119).

Users can now choose from a variety of alternative packages, such as MyDiary.org and Opendiary.com, in addition to open diaries on the internet. There are also multiple weblog services that require registration or even identification by a member, such as "Dead Journal, LiveJournal, Blurty, Blogger, Xanga, and Diary Land". Although the formats differ in look and digital capability, they all serve the same purpose. Weblogs are similar to dynamic material items in that their contents change frequently and are not intended to be printed. (Neef et al.,2006:120).

Weblogs are now widely available on the Internet; some resemble conventional paper diaries, whereas others have evolved into fully interactive formats that have become entrenched in online culture(Neef et al.,2006:128).

The diarist who uses an online diary typically uses monikers for himself, family, and friends ("dd" for "dear daughter" or more customized monikers like Miss A., Mr. 13, or My Princess), and he rarely mentions his birthday or gender in the text. People can connect with others using this method without exposing their genuine identity(Ben-Amos, B., & Ben-Amos, D.,2020:418).

Online diaries are selected as data for this research. Online personal diaries are similar to traditional paper diaries, where diarists write about their daily activities, feelings, desires, disappointments, and broken resolutions. However, online diaries differ from paper diaries in several important features that make diary writers write their online diaries: Firstly, privacy. The diarist can have complete peace of mind that their thoughts are safe and secure this service is password protected and secure. Secondly, the flexibility of online diaries, it is difficult for diarists to carry their diaries with them at all times. So downloading a diary app or using the online diary service, enable diarists to view their diary anytime and anywhere. They only require a computer with an internet connection. Finally, an online diary is easy and simple; everyone realizes how to keep a diary and utilize the internet. As a result, switching to an online diary platform is relatively straightforward. It even simplifies a difficult process by allowing users to access it right at one's fingers.

Diary and Style

An author's writing style determines how thoughts are represented through language. As a result, understanding the content of a book depends on how an author uses words and literary features. The author's writing style can be defined by word choice, tone, professional or informal language, and so on. Unique stylistic aspects are used according to the author's goal, audience, and genre. It is essential to realize how a text is generated in order to judge a diarist's style. It is not what the author says while it is how he conveys it when it comes to literary style. As a result, several aesthetic aspects in diary writing have been interpreted as expressions of femininity or responses to women's social settings, whereas in truth, they are common to both men and women's diary writing and should be viewed as responses to the genre's basic demands (Jackson,2010:4).

The trace is rhetorically incomplete in the case of diary writing since there are no standards the writer can follow, unless we accept Lejeune's view that there is a liability not to lie that is "the law of gravity: inescapable" (Lejeune,2009:204). Because all those diarists who are not really writing for publishing are simply writing for themselves in the future. The diary, as Lejeune phrased it, has no audience to dazzle or impress. Although some diaries, such as Anne Frank's diary, were written and edited with the intention of being published, the vast majority of the diaries were written by people who either refused to publish them or refused to grant their consent for them to be released. If diarists do not read their own work, they have no idea who could be reading it. The lack of such a reader for most diaries leads in the open-endedness of diary creation, which Anna Jackson describes as "a formal characteristic in itself.". As examples of rhetorical methods in diaries that promote this open-endedness, Jackson (2010) mentioned parataxis, the use of incomplete sentences, and notations like the ampersand. She even said how the dash is a fundamental component of diary rhetoric that is not evident in other genres of writing because a writer does not have to complete a thought if he or she does not want to; since the diarist is fully aware of the message he is writing and does not have to deliver it to others (Ben-Amos, B., & Ben-Amos, D., 2020:65).

The fragmented, interrupted narrative that emerges from the accumulation of individual entries is said to entail a fragmentary, interrupted writing style. When one examines the wording of the diary, Judy Nolte Lensinck discovers a personal, clear voice (Jackson, 2010:115).

Linguistic Differences between men and women's style:

Regardless of the views from which they performed their research or the methodology they used, the experts advocate the growth of gender differences research. In the field of linguistics, Robin Lakoff invented a study on gender disparities. She coined the term "female language," and her book "Language and Women's Place (1973)" piqued linguists' interest in the subject. Lakoff noted several aspects of female language in her work, including the following:

Specialized vocabulary. Females, in contrast to males, like to use more specific color terms like mauve, azure, lavender, beige, and yellow. Furthermore, they like to employ tangible terms with a strong connection to reality.

(1) Milder expletives. Females use expletives in a softer tone, whereas males use them more forcefully. For example, in Friends, Joe and Chandler frequently utter the phrase "shit or damn it," but female actors frequently utter milder expletives such as "go to hell." Different methods of speech may result from the management of social customs.

(2) Empty adjectives. To convey their sentiments, females frequently utilize words such as cute, divine, and charming.

(3) Tag questions. Though both males and females utilize tag questions in some situations, females use tag questions more frequently than males, that is, when expressing their ideas, tag questions are their preferred method of communication, even when they are certain of what they want to say. Their goal is to demonstrate that they desire to be noticed by others.

(4) intonation. Females tend to employ a rising tone even in declarative sentences, thus a rising tone has indicated their indecision and uncertainty.

(5) Super polite form. Females are often more courteous than males. They like to communicate in a non-directive manner. Consider the following example: "I was wondering whether it was possible for you to hand me that pen?"

(6) Grammar is very strict. Females generally talk with a formal tone, not just in terms of language but also in terms of pronunciation They never use terms like "ain't" or "goin".

(7) Humor and joke-telling. Females' language is devoid of humor; they talk less funnily than men. Females are not naturally gifted at coming up with jokes or comprehending them. For example, have been heard of great classic and comedic figures like Mr. Bean and Chaplin, but there are no female comedy characters that can be compared to them.

(8) Females are using more intensifiers than males, such as "terribly", "awfully", "so" , "quite", "beautiful," and other phrases.

While Ponsonby (1923:29) points out that there are some obvious differences between women's and men's diaries. Women, if they write at all, prefer to write a lot. If there are any women who

have kept daily brief notes, they must be exceptional; the idea of documenting minor details of daily life on a routine basis does not seem to appeal to a feminine mind. They prefer the memoir or letter style because it provides them more freedom to express themselves. Women have been known to write a lot of letters. This could keep a journal challenging for them. If they are denied this outlet, they are inclined to vent their frustrations in a diary. Lady Mary Coke endeavored to bring the two together, but she was not successful in either. Women tend to be more cautious and less likely to express oneself than men. The rediscovered diaries of English women diarists show that they are less dismal and contemplative, and prefer objective storytelling (Ibid.).

In truth, there are substantial distinctions between men and women's styles, which may be seen in their employment of rhetorical devices in writing a diary.

Rhetorical Devices:

It is a language-based method for improving the persuasiveness of a piece of writing. It is a technique employed by a speaker or writer to persuade a readers or audience to look at a subject in a new way. A rhetorical method is one that is designed to create emotional reactions in the audience while also presenting a sensible argument for a particular point of view or actions. Rhetorical devices include repetition, parallelism, simile, and metaphor:

a. Parallelism : Parallelism is defined as the repetition of the same syntactic structure in two or even more successive phrases. It is the process of creating a sentence in such a way that it follows a parallel pattern. (Ahmed,2021:412)

b. Repetition: A literary technique in which a phrase or word is repeated multiple times. Repetition can take so many different forms that it's hard to classify it as a single figure of speech. Instead, repetition is viewed as a broad term that incorporates a wide range of more specific figures of speech, each of which exploits repetition in a unique way.

c. Simile: Is a direct comparison of one object to another from a different category. A simile as well as a comparison is two different things. The phrase "comparison" refers to a comparison of the two things from the same category to see how similar or different they are.

d. Metaphor: A figure of speech in which someone or something is compared to another without using the words 'similar' or 'like' to convey implied meaning. "It's a mapping method between two distinct conceptual regions," says the author. (Simpson, 2004, p. 41). The target domain is the set of concepts that will be used to construct the metaphorical structure. Furthermore, Leech and Short (2007: 21) believe that poetic metaphor leads people to reject literal meaning in favor of making sense, i.e. finding meaning by paraphrasing.

Method

The study includes a stylistic analysis of ten English-language diaries. The researcher chose the diaries that are written in the diary applications (online diary) for ease of access. The researcher chosen the diaries of ten diaries, five of them belong to men and the other five belong to women. The selected data are 20 years and older, without taking into account the cultural level

of the diarist. The texts have been selected on the basis that they narrate the writer's daily life, including feelings, thoughts, and activities. The texts range from 300 to 500 words.

With the aim of looking at the diarists' use of rhetorical devices, the analysis is performed according to the modified model of linguistic and stylistic categories introduced by Leech and Short (2007). The checklist provides a "methodological basis" for collecting relevant linguistic data from the text for the purpose of stylistic evaluation and offers four levels of analysis of the language choices made by the writer. These levels include lexical categories, grammatical categories, rhetorical devices, context, and association.

This study will focus on the level of rhetorical tools. Rhetorical devices will be examined for similarities, repetitions, similes and metaphors. The similarities and differences between men and women's diaries will be brought to light as far as rhetorical devices are concern

In order to show the literary significance of the language choices made by the diarist, the discussion below will provide an analysis of the diaries of five men and five women.

Data Analysis and Discussion

In this section ten diaries will be analysed stylistically to investigate the rhetorical devices used in men and women's diaries.

Men's Diaries:

Text 1:

The diarist has utilized a parallelism to demonstrate that the parts of sentences are equally important by declaring that he despises turmoil as much as he prefers stability in his life. In addition, in the second parallelism, he uses "to find" in three phrases to emphasize how important it is to discover the additional time or his new normal. Furthermore, he has repeated the word 'work' many times, emphasizing the issue of work as if it were the focus of the diary. Then he used a simile to explain how his worry wakes him up always at the same hour as if he had set a timer. He has used simile to make the notion clear and provide a complete image of what happened in his day. Finally he used another simile to describe how the rest time passed as if it were nothing. The table below illustrates the sentences that carry a rhetorical device:

Table (1): Rhetorical Devices Text (1)

Rhetorical Devices			
Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor
I hate turbulences I prefer everything....	work and sleep and back to work	my anxiety just wakes me up like clockwork...	-----

<p>I always try to find time for me...", " I am trying to find my new normal....", " I can't seem to find the time..."</p>	<p>....work.....after...work</p>	<p>Two hours sounds like a lot in theory.... I don't realize that... .</p>	<p>-----</p>
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Text 2:

The use of parallelism in the lines displays the writer's sympathy for his friend's life by explaining how much he suffered from his wife's sickness until she died, and how he is finally coming out of his shell and having stability via marriage to the new lady. Furthermore, the second parallelism represents the diarist's concerns and fears about the next critical hours in his friend's life, which places him between death and life. The diarist then repeats the term "good" to stress how his friend is a good person. See the table below:

Table (2): Rhetorical Devices in Text (2)

Rhetorical Devices			
Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor
<p>Finally he can enjoy life..../ Finally he can go out</p>	<p>My good friend.../good dad and husband This is a good guy with a good heart.</p>	<p>-----</p>	<p>-----</p>
<p>They say that the next 24 hrs will be critical / Then they said the next 48 hrs will be a sigh of relief.</p>	<p>-----</p>	<p>-----</p>	<p>-----</p>

Text 3:

Text three does not have any rhetorical devices.

Text 4:

The presence of parallelism in the text points to two things, first, the two sentences in the table below 'I'm waiting for/ I'm going for' and '.... I know / I will.' are equal in importance showing his strong desire to go on the journey in order to discover new areas. While in the third parallel sentence, parallelism adds balance and rhythm to the sentence that underlines the meteorological disparities between the two regions.

Table (3): Rhetorical Devices in Text (4)

Rhetorical Devices			
Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor
I'm waiting for my cell phone..../I'm going for a day trip...	-----	-----	-----
...I know /I will.	-----	-----	-----
....83 degrees there and / 107 degree here	-----	-----	-----

Text 5:

The diarist uses metaphor four times to paint a vivid image of almost everything he passed through in his life in a precise pictorial manner, and he used the 'ups and downs' to refer to all of the difficult phases he went on through his life, then the 'empire' and 'throne' to demonstrate how he reconfigured his life and had been proud of his success as the lord of his empire. In 'Building Empire,' he also used one repetition to underline his excitement and satisfaction in starting a new life for himself after all the awful conditions he had to go through. The use of parallel structure between the two sentences creates a link between the present and the past and explains how he arrived at his current location after much hardship and struggle. The sentences with rhetorical devices are included in the table below:

Table (4): Rhetorical Devices in Text (5)

Rhetorical Devices			
Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor
I have built a new empire.... /I have worked from nothing...	I've managed to build empires ... / I've built a new empire	-----	My life has been up and down a lot of late.
-----	-----	-----	I've managed to build empires from nothing multiple times.

-----	-----	-----	I've built a new empire and sit on my throne amazed with all that I've done to this moment.
-----	-----	-----	The gauntlet must be thrown down.

Women's Texts:

Text 1:

The diarist has used repetition to highlight the words '**fed up, miserable, equal...**' that describe the diarist current state. In addition, she has employed parallelism to add importance and clarity to the sentence to express her thoughts and desires.

Table (5): Rhetorical Devices in Women Diary Text (1)

Rhetorical devices			
Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor
puts Izzy first /our family first. / career first. / Himself first.	feeling miserable. /feeling miserable.	-----	-----
I can't do.../ I can't go out.../ I can't go home.....	getting fed up. / I'm just SO fed up feeling	-----	-----
if I want. /... if I want....	SO SO	-----	-----
We're supposed to be equal, / we're supposed to be 50/50	-----	-----	-----
I hate today. /I hate.....	-----	-----	-----

Text 2:

The diarist employs many rhetorical techniques, which are included in the table below. For instance, the employment of parallel structural components to stress specific phrases or sentences by assigning equal weight to them. She also employs repetition of the final word in

the phrase, which is extremely close to the beginning of the next sentence, to emphasize the repeated word or concept, because repetition has a reinforcing impact. The diarist employs the simile in conjunction with the word "like" to draw a connection between purchasing a snack from internet marketing and obtaining a sponsorship package. Finally, in one sentence, she has used the phrase "ladder easier to climb" to construct a metaphorical framework connecting to her professional growth. The phrase "scarred by recent move" refers to the fact that she frequently recalls her agony from the prior traumatic experience and is hesitant to repeat it.

Table (6): Rhetorical Devices in Women Diary Text (2)

Rhetorical Devices			
Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor
in the past weeks , and particularly this week	big boss' request . A request that could have	it's like I sent myself a care package!	...the ladder has become easier to climb.
help you navigate and help you make decisions	-----	-----	I'm still scarred from my most recent move .

Text 3:

The diarist focuses on underlining her desire by repeating "I want to" around five times and then expressing things or wishes (feel loved, appreciated, caressed, hugged, kissed, laugh...etc.). The use of parallelism conveys a sense of urgency and longing, making the readers understand her desperate need for self-expression along with love, care, and attention. In terms of word repetition, she does so to further clarify her intention. For example, the word(wrong) is repeated several times, indicating that it focuses on the mistakes she has done during her life and that her whole life is made up of faults. She also uses the term (mistakes) as a synonym for (wrong). The use of repetition connects the sentences together. The table below explains the rhetorical devices in the sentences:

Table(7): Rhetorical Devices in Women Diary Text (3)

Rhetorical devices			
Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor
I wanna feel... / I wanna laugh.../ I wanna have....	I know its wrong , but hell, my whole life is wrong , whats one more thing wrong (<u>epiphora</u>)	----- -----	-----
I wanna be able to	I have made	-----	-----

say.../ I wanna be able to run....	mistakes...? Mistakes that... .	-----	
...you can't handle/ I can handle	believe in God,..... God believes	----- ---	----- -
I look sad..../I look tired... .	I would give everything up, everything, just to be happy.	----- ---	----- -

Text 4:

In some sentences, the diarist employs parallelism to convey the similarity of objects such as "love" to the shoreline and "walk." Furthermore, parallelism gives the narration a definite rhythm and its similarity produces a background to stress the necessary words that explain what the diarist intends, such as: '...what we want and where we want to go and how we want to...'. The usage of metaphor, on the other hand, provides a visual element in a lovely and engaging way. Furthermore, she has embellished her phrases with metaphorical terms. The table below shows the rhetorical devices:

Table (8): Rhetorical Devices in Women Diary Text (4)

Rhetorical devices			
Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor
I love a good beach, and I certainly love a good walk...	-----	-----but it's kind of like drinking an okay glass of wine.
...what we want and where we want to be and how we want to....	-----	-----	"if peace is the pool, then feelings are the fish."
...Just needjust release	-----	-----	"If peace is the beach, then feelings are the waves."

Text 5:

The major rhetorical device in the diary goes to the parallelism which gives emphasis to what she wants, as in the clauses "to enjoy..." and "I want to...", and she expresses her dramatic feeling by raising three rhetorical questions, using the same structures "How do I..." and this parallelism adds clarity to the text. The second rhetorical device used is the repetition of the

sentence ‘my brother is dying’ which creates a tragic and sad atmosphere that conveys the writer’s feeling of sadness.

Table (9): Rhetorical Devices in Women Diary Text (5)

Rhetorical devices			
Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor
I want to enjoy Christmas, / To enjoy the Secret.../ to enjoy the Christmas Party	My brother is dying. My brother is dying.	-----	-----
I want to bake,/ I want to hear.../ I want to feel...	-----	-----	-----
How do I tell them their father is dying? / how do I tell them about who he is, or was?/ how do I talk to him?	-----	-----	-----

Results:

This study reports the stylistic analyses of ten diaries to find the differences between men and women's English diaries in using rhetorical devices and it is found that men use fewer rhetorical techniques than women.

Men used nineteen rhetorical techniques, including eight parallel structures, five repetitions, two similes, and four metaphors. The table below provides these figures and shows that text (no.:3) does not use any rhetorical techniques.

Table (10) : Total Rhetorical Devices Numbers in Men's Diaries

Text number	Rhetorical Devices Numbers				Total
	Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor	
Text 1	2	2	2	-----	6
Text 2	2	1	-----	-----	3
Text 3	-----	-----	-----	-----	----
Text 4	3	-----	-----	-----	3

Text 5	1	2	-----	4	7
Total	8	5	2	4	19

While women use thirty (30) rhetorical devices in their diary writings, according to the table below. They have used seventeen (17) parallel phrases, seven (7) repetitions, one (1) simile sentence, and five (5) metaphors. As a result, women surpass men in using rhetorical devices.

Table (11) : Total Rhetorical Devices Numbers in Women's Diaries

Text number	Rhetorical Devices Numbers				Total
	Parallelism	Repetition	Simile	Metaphor	
Text 1	5	3	-----	-----	8
Text 2	2	1	1	2	6
Text 3	4	2	-----	-----	6
Text 4	3	-----	-----	3	6
Text 5	3	1	-----	-----	4
Total	17	7	1	5	30

The researcher proposes the following diagram to illustrate the difference in rhetorical strategies used by men and women:

Figure (14): Men and Women's Rhetorical Devices

Women are the finest writers who utilize rhetorical techniques in their works because they offer the text emotional force. Women have utilized sixteen (16) parallel sentences, as seen in the figure above. Men, on the other hand, have only employed eight (8) sentences, with parallelism being the most commonly used rhetorical device by both men and women. Women, however, employ parallelism more than men, since it is a linguistic phenomenon that draws the reader's attention and adds balance, rhythm, and most crucially, clarity to the phrase.

Furthermore, the recurrence of the phrase aims to keep the diarists' feelings and thoughts in focus. Men have used five (5) repeated words, whereas women have used eight (8). A simile is used in writings with a small number of phrases. There are only two similes in men's texts and one in women's texts. Because diaries are written in plain language with labels and depict daily activities. Direct speech makes things clearer than a simile. Furthermore, because the metaphor is commonly used in everyday conversation, women employ five metaphorical statements while males use four.

Conclusion

The researcher has drawn the following conclusions based on the results of the stylistic analyses:

1. The diarists have employed rhetorical devices in writing their daily diaries. They have utilized four types i.e. parallelism, repetition, metaphor, and simile. Women are found to use rhetorical devices more rhetorical devices than men.
2. Each rhetorical device has a function; for example, certain rhetorical devices serve to increase emotional intensity and give emphasis to some ideas in the text. The most common sort of rhetorical device in diaries is parallelism, which is used to demonstrate that the ideas in parts or sentences are of equivalent significance. Parallelism also gives the phrase a sense of balance and rhythm, as well as intelligibility. And repetition is often used to accentuate a point and make a speech simpler to understand. Parallelism and repetition are the most widely employed techniques in diaries, which are spontaneous and emotive genres produced to focus on the writer's daily activities.
3. Other types of rhetorical devices, such as simile, are used to avoid misunderstanding and ambiguity. In addition, the other rhetorical device, i.e., the metaphor does not only make what is abstract and tangible unfamiliar known, but it also enlivens by appealing to the reader's imagination. Further, it confirms another connectivity in the oneness of all things by demonstrating a relationship between objects that appear to be foreign to each other. These two rhetorical devices are little used in diaries probably because of diarists' straightness in writing their diaries and because the language of the diary is close to the form of speech.
4. Diaries are personal daily writings that people keep to record events, experiences, and feelings. Only one day's worth of events is put down in these records. A diarist writes about his day, thoughts, ideas, and internal struggles with clarity and transparency, as if he was writing just for himself.
5. The diaries subjects include a wide range of topics, including job, life, feelings, ideas, relatives, weather, key days, issues, personal growth, and so on.

6. Diaries vary in substance based on the motivations that push the diarist to write, such as personal diaries, dream diaries, academic diaries, and so on. One of the things that motivates scholars to learn further about diaries is the personalized aspect of diary writing.

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References

1. Ahmed, M.(2020). *The Linguistics of Translation*.Amman: Dar Academic For Publishing And Distributing Co.
2. Ben-Amos, B., & Ben-Amos, D. (Eds.). (2020). *The Diary: The Epic of Everyday Life*. Indiana University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvxcrxgp>
3. Carter, R., and Stockwell, P. (2008). *The Language and Literature Reader*. New York: Routledge,
4. Fothergill, R. A. (1974). *Private chronicles: A study of English diaries*. London: Oxford University Press.
5. Galstyan, A. (2014).‘Several linguostylistic issues of literary diary’, 16(May), p. 7. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/256546698>
6. Hussein, Khalid. (2017). *A Corpus-Driven Approach to Stylistic Analysis of a Lexical Richness Curve*. GRIN Verlag.
7. Jackson, A.(2010). *Diary Poetics: Form and Style in Writers’ Diaries, 1915–1962*.New York: Routledge,.
8. Jeffries, L. & McIntyre, D.(2010). *Stylistics*. Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from <http://www.bookfinder.com/> (15May 2016).
9. Lakoff, R. (1973). Language and woman's place. *Language in Society*, 1(2), 45–80. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0047404500000051>
10. Leech, G. & Short M. (2007). *Style in Fiction: a Linguistic Introduction to English Fictional Prose*. (2nd Ed.). Edinburgh: Pearson Education Limited.
11. Lejeune, Ph.(2009).*On Diary*. University of Hawai`i Press.
12. Neef, S., van Dijck, J.& Ketelaar, E. (2006).*Sign Here! Handwriting in the Age of New Media*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press.
13. Ponsoy, A.(1923). *English Diaries*. London: Methuen & Co.
14. Short, M. (1996). *Exploring the language of poems, plays, and prose*. London: Longman.
15. Simpson, P. (2004). *Stylistics: a Resource Book for Students*. London: Routledge.
16. Skirgailo (2006).*To Teaching methodology to work on compositions of non-traditional genres*. - M.: Russian word.

Appendix

Men and Women's Diaries

A. Men Diaries :

Text 1: Doomedforlife

2021-08-09 09:42:00 (UTC)

267 word

new normal

I hate turbulences in life, good or bad. I prefer everything to be normal and settled. I always try to find time for me to just laze around no matter what, and I am trying to find my new normal at my job with my schedule. With me working for 10 plus hours..I cant seem to find the time to even go to the gym or even step out of my house let alone time to just lie in my bed and relax. My shift timing starts at 12 in the afternoon and ends at 10pm wiith additional unofficial extra work hours. Nowadays i wake up, turn on my laptop...work...after work for about 2 hours do my daily chores, watch youtube, chat with friends and listen to some music and go to sleep. Two hours sounds like a lot in theory but for me...i dont even realize that i have used up all my free time with just that. I cant even sleep in the mornings even though my shift starts at 12...my anxiety just wakes me up like clockwork because i am always anxious that someone might contact me since most of the people in my team start work in the morning. It is pretty weird...no matter how much i tell myself that it will be fine even if i slept more..my brain just wont listen. So...is this going to be the new normal? Just work and sleep and back to work? I am lucky enough to have a job and earn money coz two of my friends havent been able to and they are struggling and i dont want to experience that again...but...Is this it?

Text 2: Street_smart

2020-04-13 08:51:50 (UTC)

320word

Real life issues

I got a message from our boss that my good friend at work had a stroke. He is currently in ICU. His wife can't even stay with him due to Covid 19. So sad to hear. He is such a good Dad and Husband. His first wife actually passed away. She had Lupus and he spend many years taking care of her till she passed. When he met this lady, it was a perfect match for him. Finally he can enjoy life and not just be sitting by the bedside of a sick wife. Finally he can go out and enjoy the things a normal husband and wife do.

Then this happens. All we can get now are phone updates from his wife because that all she can get too. We can't visit the hospital. They say that the next 24 hrs will be critical. What the hell does that mean? Doesn't sound good to me at all but I didn't say anything. Then they said the next 48 hrs will be a sigh of relief. What!/? Does this mean that he could die? WTH?! Hard enough with them having to deal with Covid, they have this life and death issue to deal with too?

They are also just newlyweds so they never really got to have a honeymoon yet due to financial burdens they both had. Living together was making it easier for them and they were finally

getting out of the hole.. then this happens. Sheez. I feel so bad for him, my friend of 19 years now. I pray he makes it though. This is a good guy with a good heart. We are close and we can tell each other things that we don't tell anyone else at work. Sad to hear he is fighting for his life. This is life. Life is short folks. Don't think you are guaranteed another day. Make the most of it.

Text 3: Hawksbrother

2020-12-17 14:04:00 (UTC)

450 words

Snow Day

Major winter storm hit last night, and is still going. Snow at first, then a mixture, finally sleet/rain coming down now, with more snow expected in a few hours. I put those windshield covers on both cars last night just before all this fun started, and I'm quite glad of that now. Our driveway is blocked now with high snow from the plow that went down our street last night. Our erstwhile landlord hasn't cleared it yet, but I'm hoping that, with the help of all this melting rain, we can overpower it when we both need to get to work in the morning, after removing the covers.

My new aquarium is due in nlt 2000 today, but I've been unable to track it, and am getting a bit frustrated, unsure if I will EVER get the silly thing, although the other things for it came ahead of schedule. Starting to think I should have gone to DPS for it; at least then I'd have been able to bring it right home from the store instead of waiting for the stupid thing to be delivered by Fed Ex.

Matt and Wendy both tested negative for covid, much to our reliefs. Got the dishwasher and sink cleaned out finally. I'd like to give myself a haircut using our clippers, IF I can get up the gumption to just DO it.

Finally got around to listening to my audio book (Catch 22) earlier today, using my earphone. It took something like three hours, but was well worth the time. Might look at getting other audio books in the near future.

Payday tomorrow, most of which is going to Zero's financing. Bambi is working in her home office, as usual. She didn't get a day off, unfortunately.

The water in the nano tank cleared up by itself, as it normally tends to do if left alone and feeding moderated a bit. Thank God!

Got Willie working more or less up to par by erasing it and starting over, losing all the stuff accumulated over the past seven years or so.

Bambi did her holiday thing last night, getting home just as the snow was starting in earnest. That gave me time to get Zero tarped before the shit REALLY came down.

They switched vans with me for the last two days of this week, and will give me yet ANOTHER one come Monday morning. When will this game of musical vans END over there? Annoying as hell!

Lots of caffeine today. Three large cups of cold tea, and I finished that gallon of Arizona Tea Bambi got me a few days ago, finally. One beer left for this evening.

Life goes on.

Text 4: Jon

2011-07-09 18:00:47 (UTC)

483 word

Day Trip

I'm waiting for my cell phone to charge and then I'm going for a day trip up north. It's supposed to be 83 degrees there and 107 here with little shade. They are also expecting cloudy conditions with showers and thunderstorms. I can't remember when it last rained here, never mind a completely cloudy day - it's been months. Constant sun here.

I went to the dog park this morning, arriving there around 4:30 before the sun came up. I was there alone with my dogs for about a half hour and it was nice and quiet. Others started arriving around 5:00. I took a real deep nap when I got home and then cleaned up the apartment. I decided to go to Walmart and buy a large cooler and lawn chair for my road trips. Nope - can't afford this, but did it anyway. I need some sanity and need to get away now and then.

I won't be going to the cabin, but I'm going to places that will be special to me. I'll need to discover them, and I know I will. I'm driving to Sedona first. It's going to be hot there, so I don't want to stay long. They say there is a space/time vortex there. This place draws retirees, New Age folks, and artists. It's a place to behold and when first seen it is mesmerizing. The main street is filled with touristy shops but all around are large red rock mountains, somewhat the color of a hot ember.

As you leave Sedona, you travel a winding road through part of the largest Ponderosa Pine forest in the world. It's amazing, because this forest is one organism, each tree connected to another through their root system.

A river runs parallel to the road I will be following. Some sections of the river run slow, while others rush white water around glacial boulders. There are plenty of places to pull over and have a picnic, which I plan to do. Just further north is a Scenic Overlook which is absolutely beautiful, overlooking the canyon and river. There, Native Americans sell silver, turquoise, leather goods, hard-carved pieces, and other wares. None of this is junk and it's authentic, made right here in Arizona, probably around the Navajo Nation.

After the overlook, I'm going to Flagstaff. This winding road will take you straight into town. Flagstaff is the home of Northern Arizona University. It is also the home to Lowell Observatory, a space research facility with a very large telescope.

But my plan is to get an ice cream in Flagstaff and then head home on I-17, which can be very tricky as there are some very steep grades. (Flagstaff is more than a mile high). So, that's my plan for the day, even though it's getting close to noon. I wish this phone would hurry up and charge!

Text 5: Prophetess

2021-06-02 21:10:49 (UTC)

488 words

The path forward

I have to say the ride has been an interesting one since it started. My life has been up and down a lot of late. I have been looking back today. I really shouldn't but when I'm sitting here fighting off airplane crud, I can't help it sometimes. Starting my walk through the first steps in school has brought me back a little. Every win and every loss that has led to here. I can say that I'm a little more blessed than some I know. Even when I have had L's I've still managed to come out on top. I've managed to build empires from nothing multiple times. I used those to try to say how strong I am. No matter how much I've hidden my weaknesses, I'm the one that has had to live with them. I've been through things that would kill most or drive them to kill themselves. Yes, I've even self-medicated. Still, I haven't been dead yet.

I have been blessed with amazing friends, family, kids, and so much more. I have a group of friends in my amazing hobby. This time I'm making each step with purpose and I've been walking pretty far since I was dumped off in Georgia. I've built a new empire and sit on my throne amazed with all that I've done to this moment. I've worked from nothing and now I'm in a place that I don't worry about much except the occasional burn out and crud from doing a turnaround flight to see an old friend. I've got a really good job that I love (and miss being away from today) and I have school starting on Friday. Even if some things aren't where I want them to be, that cat's getting belled this weekend.

It's been a hell of a ride. New things, new life, and it's only getting better. Even the trip was worth it for my soul. There were a few things that tried to bring me down, but I got past those as well. I do want to go back in time, but for now I'm content with where I am. I had my taste and what I needed while I'm there. I'm slowly getting over the crud and look forward to going to work tomorrow. I don't know if I'm looking forward to the weekend and what's coming with it, but it has to happen. The gauntlet must be thrown down. There's no looking back now. I can't lament the past any longer. There's nothing more than forward now. I'm excited but nervous. I'm told though that that's a good thing. It means that I'm ready for the next leg of my life.

B. Women's Diaries:

Text 1: Wedonttalk Miserable

2012-01-13 10:29:13 (UTC)

365 word

Miserable

I'm feeling miserable today. That seems to be all I come on here for

now, to complain about the bad days. I guess I'm just getting fed up with how my life is panning out. I have all the things I want, izzy, Dean, our own home..marriage. But I feel like I don't get to make any decisions anymore. I feel like I'm not important anymore, like y choices and opinions get overlooked. It's all because I'm not the one that's working ofcourse. Only I didn't have much of a choice in that either really..

I'm the one that puts izzy first, our family first. deans the one who pits his career first. Himself first. I WANT to go to work..I just feel like I can't yet. I can't put izzy in full time nursery at 5months old. It's not fair. So I'm just going to have to go on feeling like the crap half of the couple, the one who gets all of the bad so their partner doesnt have to. Although saying that, Dean makes me feel guilty at every opportunity about the fact that he pays for everything.

I'm getting sick of feeling like crap. I can't do ANYTHING I want. I can't go out if I want. I can't go home if I want..It's all up to Dean. Dean makes the decisions. Because Dean brings the money and I look after Izzy. We're supposed to be equal, we're supposed to be 50/50 when it comes to Izzy, but it just feels like I have her 90% of the time and once every few months Dean will have her for a 3 hour period and I have feel SO SO grateful about it!! I have to 'make it up to him' 'show him hoe grateful I am' like he's doing me a favour taking care of his own daughter by himself.

Uh. Im just SO fed up feeling like this. Its like our first year together all over again. Dean can do no wrong and sees everything the right way while I'm never good enough, always trying to make the wrong decision. I hate today. I hate feeling miserable.

Text2: Esmeralda_Bramble

2021-01-15 15:57:37 (UTC)

381 Word

Boss Babe

HAHAHAHAHA, I never thought that I would feel okay being a "boss". But in the past weeks, and particularly this week, I'm feeling it more. Thanks to the folks who resigned year, the ladder has become easier to climb. Didn't think I'd feel comfortable "leading" people. It does help when you have a good team and if you understand what you're doing most of the time. But somehow, even if you don't know everything about something, there are people who will help you navigate and help you make decisions. I am fortunate though I work with smart and considerate people. I'm enjoying giving guidance on what people should do and just checking their work. It's liberating to be able to delegate tasks and free up

my time to do something more productive. ;p
 My biggest achievement so far, yes, I'm owning it, was to push back to our big boss' request. A request that could have compromised our integrity and I stood up for it. I didn't have to raise my voice or fight with but providing a rational argument helped. Or maybe my big boss was just testing me if I'm just a "Yes" man. But yeah, pretty happy about that. LOL.

On the "darker" side of my week, I heard back from 3 companies I applied to last year. The first one sounded promising, I was going on to the next stage of the application but they quickly took it back and rejected me. I talked to 2 more, and I don't think I will get in there anyway. First, some essential skills they're looking for, I don't have. Second, they are in different parts of the country and at this point, I don't want to do a crosscountry relocation. I'm still scarred from my most recent move. So overall, I will likely stay in my current company and learn more skills before I go out to a more competitive world. In the meantime, I got my snacks (OMG, I found an online store and was able to buy snacks from home, it's like I sent myself a care package!), I got food for the next week. Since DC's in lockdown until after the inauguration, I will be staying home and eating! :) Have a good weekend everyone!

Text 3: Gabby

2013-07-04 10:48:52 (UTC)

435word

so....

So, i work till 10 tonight, but gotta be back at work at 6am, someone messed up the schedule. I am at a loss, what to think or do. Ma had a car accident an my car is in the shop. Dont know yet if it is totaled. So much garbage, I wanna run away. I really feel the need to connect with someone, and I dont just mean sex. I wanna feel loved, appreciated, touched, hugged, kissed. I wanna laugh with some one, i wanna have some one i can be myself with, i wan to be able to say what i think and feel with out worry. I need a deep down, soul touching connection. I wanna be able to run to some one when I hurt for comfort, and in return, they come to me for comfort, that its me they wanna be near, me they wanna spend time with. Is that too much to as for? I guess in life it is. Are we all doomed to be unhappy? No, not all, I see people, couples laugh, tease each other, kiss each other, hug, and all the while i wonder, am i so bad that I cant be loved like that? I keep thinking that in a prior life I must of really fucked someone or others up so bad, that I am now, in this life paying for it. Sometime ago. i started cutting, i never understood how people could do that, but now sometime it seems to help. I know its

wrong, but hell, my whole life is wrong, whats one more thing wrong to add to the list. Yes I have made mistakes, but why am i still paying for them? Mistakes that even now have had consequences. I wanna say i believe in God, but the problem is I donth think God believes in me. I forget the verse but it goes something like , He will not give you such a burden that you cant handle (i am paraphrasing) Well, i dont know how much more i can handle, cause i give up on life on love on happiness on anything good. It has come to my attention that I look sad all the time, that i look tired and that i never smile anymore. I am trying to "look" better even if i dont feel it. I know if I die the only ones thay would miss me are my mom, brother and Ma. I would give everything up, everything, just to be happy. As long as i have Ma, i think i would be ok.

Text 4: Me, Myself, and Yy

2021-07-28 23:53:41 (UTC)

545 word

How Does Energy Coexist with Expectation?

it is funny to me how some places feel a certain way over others. I have been to my fair share of beaches and beach towns, but I am learning that they all feel differently to me. Right now, in my current vacation location in south Florida, I spent the day interacting with the beach scene, and while it is beautiful here and there is a lot of energy, it isn't energy that fits me. Strange how that works.

I love a good beach, and I certainly love a good walk along a beach in the early morning or the evening time. I just don't feel like this beach is "my beach." Plus, it sort of brings up memories of a location where I did feel the energy strongly, but it was energy tied to an important person in my life and past intimate memories we shared there. So, I guess that script is re-writing my current experience on this beach, but even that aside, it still doesn't feel like me. I am still enjoying it, but it's kind of like drinking an okay glass of wine. You won't not drink it, but you have definitely tasted better.

This, of course, leads back to expectations. I guess this place is not meeting whatever expectations I had for it. It's been good to relax and chill and read and write, etc., but I am looking forward to being back home with what is familiar. So, the expectation of familiarity is missing maybe? Suppose I come back in a year or so, would that mean I might feel more fondness for it? Perhaps. If I met someone on this beach and my whole world changed as a result, would that be enough to stir the significance factor? Perhaps, although extremely unlikely. Speaking of expectations, here is a quote I read that might apply some: "We create pictures of what we want and where we want to be and how we want to

be seen, then hold them out ahead of us as some strange form of gold we must have, expecting life to conform to these images." As I consider this quote more, clearly I have lackluster expectations of this place and this beach, but that doesn't mean it couldn't become something I would never dream would be a possibility.

I think this is true of people as well. We get caught up in our expectations of others and forget about observing the energy that is present in the moment or in the setting. It's hard not to expect to have expectations. It seems like a perfectly normal human endeavor, and yet we also find that our expectations also trip us up way more than they surprise us. Or maybe that is just me. I am starting to learn to just let myself be surprised and go with the flow. And on that note, maybe I just need to let this beach wash over me in whatever way it is meant to and just release my expectations (if that is possible).

Mark Nepo says, "If peace is the pool, then feelings are the fish." Maybe I should consider, "If peace is the beach, then feelings are the waves." Something like that... :)

Text 5: ClosedDoor

2020-12-01 21:49:00 (UTC)

588words

My Brother is Dying

Since i last wrote, Months ago now. I have Had Covid, dealt with the being sick, and getting tested, and being quarantined. I have Done so much work after i was sick trying to catch up on the things that i couldn't do while i was isolated in a single room for 2 weeks completely alone.

I have felt like i have aged years in the last several months....but that seems to be the theme of 2020. Thanksgiving was ruined because i had covid and then my household had to quarantine, thankfully though they didn't get sick. I have several meetings coming up with work, been to a couple this last week, i've been trying so hard to stay on the positive side, of being happy that it's christmas time, Because i have wanted nothing but christmas time for months, but now that it's here i feel like i'm battling depression and things that Genuinely are sad and hard and difficult, i mean take today for instance it's the first of December we got our Christmas tree up and lights on yesterday and we were supposed to decorate the tree with the kids today, and right when i head down stairs to go do that i get the phone call, the phone call from my brother in the hospital who says that he had cancer, Mylofibrosis and or Leukemia. they give him 5 years at best, he's in his 30s. My relationship with him is rocky, but i'm still not down to lose another brother.

I've already lost one. Which is part of why December is a hard time for me because the 12th is Levi's Death date. I was hoping and praying that Robert wouldn't have Cancer that he would be okay (and he still could i know) it's not over till it's over but the line that keeps playing in my

head over and over is "My brother is dying." "My Brother is dying" My brother is Dying" Everything feels heavy. And i feel like crying, but i also feel like i just want to be happy, i want to enjoy christmas, To enjoy the Secret santa exchange i'm in, to enjoy the christmas Party i have on the 16th, the Christmas lock in on the 20ths, Friendsmas somewhere before that, I want to bake, and sit up late at night alone in the living room with a cup of coffee enjoying the darkness with the only light coming from the tree, i want to hear all the christmas music and Go to christmas in the park, i want to feel carefree and not have this sadness Laying on my shoulders like wet clothes that just weigh you down and stick to you in the worst way.

I'm scared of losing my brother and with it, the hope that our family could have restoration. I don't know how to carry a torch for his children which i'm raising who are to young to know this, to young to understand. How do i tell them their father is dying? how do i tell them about who he is, or was? how do i talk to him? all serious like every time could be the last or joke and gloss over the seriousness in favor of giving him a moment of rest from the idea of death and what this will mean. I'm too tired to think right now. and my heart is to heavy. Tomorrow is a new day, may it bring new air to breathe.